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Wed, 4/6 8:43PM • 53:46

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

kid, string, moment, enjoying, bit, pitch, platform, happening, hitting, happy, vibration, faster, touching, vibrating, pause, feeling, smiling, repeat, clapping, interaction

SPEAKERS

Interviewer, Observer 2

Interviewer 00:00

Okay, so first of all, talk about these interviews because a little bit atypical, so the micro phenomenological interview, I won't to ask you very specific, I won't ask you directly questions, but we'll do here is trying to pick a moment that you found interesting during the interaction with the kids. It's like, literally one moment something had happened. It could, I can be something really, really small, that sort of got your attention, or can be something very significant, but it doesn't matter. It is, it should be something that resonates with you, that comes to your attention or something. So we are not interested in understanding the usability, or, for example, the installation, we're not interested in those things. We're more interested in knowing how the kids reacted, how was your perception or on the reaction that's like, well, as an observer, right? so it's not like a technical sort of... we're not after like technical explanations about how things were working, etc, etc. And the idea is again, so you will start like, you will start remembering things, because I will be constantly asking you how were things. So we are generally very concerned about what things we do, and how things function, but not so much how things were like the process of things. So sometimes my questions might be a little bit repetitive, or it's like, imagine that this kind of interview style is more like putting the experience under a microscope. So expand it. So I will ask you, how was it? And how was this thing? And how was this thing? So to get into that very granular detail? What else? You can stop me at any moment, if you find this, that is annoying, or you don't want to reply to my questions. Or if you're tired, or you know, want to talk about things, feel free to say, you know, I am tired, I have to go, stop this bloody interview, we can do that. No problem. And also I will be you will say things and I'll be repeating those back to you to check if I've got your impressions, right. And you also feel free to correct me of saying, "Oh, that word doesn't... It's not exactly what they said" it's not or just change your, like your version of things because sometimes ones change their opinions and something open here that I'm close because distracting me. This bloody slack. Okay, all right. Okay. So first, I will ask you to, if you agree to, to bring back a specific moment that there was interesting for you. Okay. Yeah, take your time. And just let me know. Specifically, what moment was that one? Okay.

Observer 2 03:21

If you don't mind, maybe for me, it's easier to recollect something because also we are talking about almost one week ago now.

Interviewer 03:31

Yes. Of course

Observer 2 03:32

So I will just maybe, like say just things loud, just to have my just to remember something because there were a couple of moments that I just found nice super, super nice. I got super, you know, interested in this. The two kids that were in the middle I don't know because of my position in the room. But anyway, the two in the middle. So those two kids... I got the impression they were enjoying a lot. So maybe that's why I was just looking at them. And [long pause] so there is... this, of course, anything that they can say... I mean, I believe it's of course, just my kind of interpretation of it. But I remember this, two more. Okay. Three, okay, wait. If I go in just talking, I'm just doing this whole thing. There are three things: one that made me a bit kind of sad and one is stat that they found super cool. Basically, the one little bit that they found sad, was actually the the girl on the on the on the top right platform that I had the feeling she was not... I don't know, if she was not enjoying or she was feeling a little bit uncomfortable, or anything or this is just you know, due to, you know, maybe her, you know... how to say... her, you know, difficulties, you know, motor skills and everything. So I don't really know. And I don't want to kind of impose my perception of that, but was like, if is she like feeling bad because the vibration of everything. And I think that was fine, because then at the end of the pedagogue said that everyone was enjoying that, so so I can feel less sad about that. But the beginning was like, I don't know, if she's really very limited in moving, or it's really something that like of vibration is too strong, or whatever. So that was one thing. But the two kids in the middle to me, they were enjoying that so much in different ways. So if you want me to pick one moment, or if I can just say two moments, I don't know, one for each. There was the kid in the second platform. I think I even mentioned this to him, while we were there, that I had the feeling that he was enjoying a lot. He was like, looking at the at the string, and then, you know, moving it. And there was a moment that I mean, this is what I think his platform was often without vibration. And the platform of the other kid to the one on wheelchair that was as bigger platform was on the vibration, I got the feeling that he wanted to go to the other platform because there was vibration. But you know, and that just made me laugh yeah .. us just just, of course, it made me also happy because he was enjoying that and he wanted the vibration. It's always tricky to try to not see her that are not there. But in any case, I mean, he seemed to enjoy everything and also the kid in the in the wheelchair. Well, I mean, sorry, they were all in the wheelchair, but the one on the big platform. I... I had the impression that he was really *there*, like oh, I can feel the vibration. There's the light I can I can touch it. And it's it's sounding, it's vibrating. And I got the feeling that he was really happy while doing that. I mean, he was hitting the string. And then I got this feeling that he was like whoa, okay, I can do that again. It's fun. It's fun. It's working. This is the feeling that that I got. So yeah, these are you know certain things I didn't really focus too much on the first girl because it was a bit far from me. I was more in the middle so that that's that's why but yeah, this second kid the the one that to me was trying to reach the other platform

Interviewer 08:51

it seems that that story in particular say one that repeats the most. You have three moments, right? You have one with the girl or the corner that was apparently sad and so made you feel sad. You have this another one with the kid that was apparently very happy in his wheelchair. And there was a moment

when the platform when off and you felt you had the impression that he was trying to reach the other big platform when the other kid was who was also enjoying himself. You saw that he was kind of present... he was there.

Observer 2 09:28

I think I think he was enjoying what was happening. He was you know, when you have this moment, like you know you do something and you just get the reaction from some from I don't know, I touch the table. Okay, well, it's fine. It's moving. Instead that kind of feeling like oh, it's all it's moving. Cool. I would just do that again. I had that feeling like someone that is not just acknowledging that something is happening. but more like, family... enjoying that? This is the impression this is the, the kid on the on the bigger platform. Yeah, so this is the third string. And the other key that was mentioning was the one on the second platform that when his session will be his also because you know, I was standing on and off the haptics are really remember which haptics were on and off. So, so this kid on the second platform... you know, it's also funny because... Okay, Another thing if I can add, since I was in the control room, and when I go out to the control room, I enter in the sound forest, and the first thing that they see is the kid on the on the second platform, I could really see his face when entering the room. There was like, so, like... I felt that was happy to be there. That was nice. I mean, it was you know, knowing all these troubles in, you know, taking the bus coming to the museum, getting into the room, everything was like, okay, at least they are having a good time.

Interviewer 11:27

I will suggest you. This is a suggestion, because it seems that you have like three specific moments that you have. It's really well defined what is happening in the first platform... and the second platform and the third one, right, the big one, is that, okay, so I will suggest you what if we focus on the kid on the second platform. At some point about who he started going to third anyways, but we can talk about it. Yeah. Okay, so if you agree, the first thing I'll ask you to do is to... so you were saying that when you were in the control room, and sort of go... you went out of the control room, the first thing you saw was a kid like the face of a kid?

Observer 2 12:17

Yeah.

Interviewer 12:19

Okay,

Observer 2 12:20

is that's the string that is kind of immediately in, you know, in terms of positioning the room is just out of the control room. So I was kind of forced to see him, but it was nice, because I saw the kid and enjoying that saw I was like,

Interviewer 12:37

What did you see that he was enjoying? How do you know?

Observer 2 12:41

I don't know. I just I think I saw his... Yeah, I think I just saw his face. And this is the first thing that I saw. So... you know, I think I, I kind of... also this very big smile when you have your mouth open like, Whoa, cool. So or at least this is how I interpreted but this is what what I saw this kid like with the eyes just looking up because the light. I was like, oh, and and then yeah, when they were touching this bit all but yeah, also the skin when they were touching, they were also you know, jumping on the on the wheelchair. So I interpret it as they're enjoying that. But yeah, I saw him like, you know, when you have your mouth open eyes a bit open, like Oh, nice. This is why Yeah, this is the thing that made me think that he was enjoying that. And then also when he was not in the wheelchair, but laying... lying... lying down on the on the floor, of course, you know, it was just there and I think in that moment, you know, after that he was trying to crawl like but yeah, I got the impression that this kid was really enjoying that...from from from his face from you know,

Interviewer 14:25

when you saw his face, so you were like in the control room and you went out and you you were in a way like sort of forced to see him because he was there the first person and he was like smiling and looking up and with a mouse and the eyes open like having this yesterday and you thought oh, he's very happy. So you remember how was the room was the were the lights on?

Observer 2 14:51

Not was off

Interviewer 14:52

It was off. So you could still

Observer 2 14:54

i Yeah, because Wait. I'm very sure it was off because I was in the control room. And I turn stuff on and off. According to the session, like, Okay, this platform must have all the haptics of this on I check. I do. I start all the thing. And then I was at... Yeah. Wait, wait, I was in charge of turning lights on and off. So I'm pretty sure that when entering the room, the light was off. Yeah, of course. I wasn't... Sorry. It's, [laughs] I was in charge of doing that. So yes, no, no, no, I start everything, I got the signal from [Observer1], that we were starting the new session, I do everything, I turned the light off, I entered the room because I needed to be in the room also to check that everything was fine. So when I entered the room, the light was clearly off. And he was just next to the string. So it was enough what I mean, it's not that that but you cannot see the face. So. So. Now, I don't know if that's true or not. But you know, maybe there was even this, this kind of light a little bit reflecting on the face because you know, it was close to the string. So when you touch it, then the string turns, you know, becomes brighter, and then you see a little bit better. But... is that true? I don't know. I don't remember. But it's it's... going back to your question. Yes. lights were off. Strings. Were on; lights in the room were off. I could see the the kid's face. Yeah, that's, that's for sure.

Interviewer 16:51

So then, when you could see the face, and it was with the eyes open the mouth, and you see this yesterday of happiness? What happened exactly after that?

Observer 2 17:06

I think just a smile back to him as first thing, because, you know, I was smiling. I don't know, I just know. Nice. And you know, I as... well as first thing, I just moved quickly to reach a position in which I could see the kids without, you know, bothering them. So for sure, this is what they did. So I was standing next to the little window in the team trying to not cover the cameras. So I entered the room. I think I saw the kid. It was cool. It was nice. I was happy about that. And then I just moved to not bother also because you have been chances were also around with the camera. So I was like, okay, I won't... I have to be here to check everything. I hope my presence will not, you know, kind of bother the kids too much. But I think it didn't. So yeah, in terms of action, the first thing I did is like probably doing like nice. Moving around the screen and then going next to the window. So and then yeah, I was there looking at... and yeah, this, I think happened. Also... just to add details. I think this, this happened, not in the first session. This I think happened more in the second and third session. Because in the first session, I think I was I mean, I was also going to the room, but I wanted to be really, really sure that everything was working, you know, in terms of the sound and everything. So they're also in the first session. I was also maybe a bit more in the control room, I guess, just to make sure that everything was really fine. And I think this happened so not when entered for the first session. I think it happened when I entered for the second or even the third section probably or the second or the third. Yes.

Interviewer 19:29

So where the kids in the wheelchair.

Observer 2 19:34

Exactly. They were in the wheelchair. So this must be for sure the second session and then when the kids started to reach the [xx] because he was on the... on the on the floor, so this wasn't a third. So I think that when it was back in the moment, that was the sort of... when I was back in the room and then I saw the kids smiling these must have been just at the beginning of the second session yes...

Interviewer 20:06

the kid at some point that string or how was the kid how was he doing?

Observer 2 20:12

no no.. he he was, he was touching the string. He...[long pause] yeah I think that the the second kid and also the third cube at last lot of interaction they they touch a lot the string or this is what I remember when?

Interviewer 20:44

Yeah, so they were touching a lot of string and how was the kid touching the screen

Observer 2 20:58

I think that yep, yep. Okay. So I think that he was next to the string. And then he was hitting the string with the hand. So...oh, wait, they just remember another thing now, but this is on the third kid. Because the second kid that was touching, hitting, okay, it was hitting the string and a little bit jumping. But I think that hitting and jumping was way stronger with the third kid. And now I think remember this thing now that when he was hitting the string, since the more you hit the, the more you know, this, it sounds like

higher in pitch, I got the feeling that he was he... was you know, kind of getting what was happening and then enjoying when the pitch was going higher. And then it was actually hitting stronger and faster. Because the string, you know, was sounding with the higher pitch. I think yeah, just know. Remember this so yeah, this was the third kid also, because I noticed that compared to the others, he had the you know, everyone at the tutor next to them, but I think that this third kid, and a little bit less of the pedagogue next to him, or her helping out in interacting with the string. So maybe, you know, he had a little bit more of autonomy or whatever. But I think that he was a little bit more autonomous compared to the others. And so it was hitting and then it was going up and then I think he even like, these little kind of little high pitched scream like things and yeah, okay... now I mean, you know, it's, it'... I think he was doing something like that, like he was hitting, then the sounds was going higher. And when the haptics was also on, when he felt the vibration, he was like, you know, even a little bit clapping the ends or something like this. Of course, we can check the video to see for these when we happen, but I remember that he was enjoying that. And now Yes, I was talking about the kid on the big platform. Yeah. So this is the third.

Interviewer 23:56

So but yeah,

Observer 2 23:58

sorry, I'm moving.

Interviewer 23:58

No, no, that's okay. It's okay. Because you were seeing the tickets at the same time. It was like living your vision. So yeah, and things were... So here I have a question. So you're saying that you were talking first about the second kid? He was like playing with the string. But then you mentioned that the third kid was also playing with the string like stronger? Because apparently he was like getting the interaction and the stronger because the stronger you get it. The higher the pitch, the stronger I

Observer 2 24:29

would say. It's not the stronger the faster, faster. Yeah.

Interviewer 24:33

Okay. So the faster you hit it, so the higher the pitch, and apparently the kid was getting it. So was this happening while the second kid was doing his thing as well?

Observer 2 24:51

I believe so. I mean, more, is

Interviewer 24:52

it something that popped up? Because I asked you about the second kid and then your just remember

Observer 2 25:00

Okay, sorry, I didn't get the question. So.. so... you know, in terms of time, I think those things were happening more or less in the same time frame. But now that I was thinking when you asked, you

know, how the kid was interacting with the string, I think about all the situation I was like, Oh, wait, but, you know, the third kid was doing even more so just, you know, association of ideas and then I went to the third kid. Yeah. Okay, but I'm pretty sure that yeah, this was happening in terms of time you know, it was happening same time frame... maybe you know... you know, I think they were really feeling you know, that sometimes the vibration was on and off. So maybe you know, this kid was hitting faster when he also felt the vibration. I think I kind of spotted a little bit of disappointment in his face when we add we turn the vibration off, and then he was hitting and then vibration was not there. So he started doing that little bit less but... you know. So this is it's hard sometimes to say these kinds of things and trying to separate what, you know. I want to see Yes. And what actually was there but I mean Yeah.

Interviewer 26:54

was a moment when you were saying, Okay, so the third kid was getting what was happening. So the faster the higher the piece, and you were controlling, like, also you were in controlling the haptics and it was a moment when the haptics was off. And you sort of spotted a bit of disappointment.

Observer 2 27:17

Yeah, this is this is... you know, it's tricky because of course, I know that the vibration was awful. But I think that they saw a little bit of disappointment in his face when he touched the string and then the platform was not doing anything

Interviewer 27:39

Could you describe tgis disappointment? How you perceive this?

Observer 2 27:44

you know, mmm [long pause] just, I'm just thinking... yeah.

Interviewer 28:00

Take your time. No worries.

Observer 2 28:05

So I think in one session, it was playing was hitting sound was you know, the pitch was higher, platform was what vibrating, he was happy, he was like, and lift clap and... and then, when I had to turn the vibration off, I had the feeling that was kind of trying to do the same that is hitting again, trying to repeat. And then I think that I kind of saw him slowing down in doing this, like, oh, wait, this is not the vibrating so maybe I will not hit anymore because it's not vibrating. This is....you know, this I'm now kind of verbalizing what I felt in that moment. So it's, you know, it's it's not one to one but yeah, I think that the it was like... Can I make a comparison?

Interviewer 29:21

Sure. Go for it!

Observer 2 29:22

It's very stupid. But you know, you go to a restaurant you had a very nice time because you and a lot of great food and then decided to go you know, again to that restaurant, then you notice that the food is

something different, and then you eat less, because okay, maybe I will not order as much as the other day because it's like the chef changed in the meanwhile, that was the thing like he was kind of cool. They will know this word in English

Interviewer 29:50

Then say it in italian...

Observer 2 29:52

"Voracce", voracious? was, I don't know when you're like, oh, this great. They want more. And then when you are in the same situation that you want the same and you feel like, Wait, I don't want more, because this is not really the same anymore! This is the kind of feeling that they got now. Again, you know, this is just what I kind of felt like, okay, he's playing a little bit less, I think he he completely understood that no, this is not kinda... this is not vibrating. So yeah. So I think this is how I kind of... can try to explain this feeling of disappointment that I believe I perceived in the his movements and interaction with the screen Yeah.

Interviewer 30:53

Yeah, perfect. So there was a moment of disappointment when you realize that, okay, so your turns the haptics off and he was like playing and you noticed that he started like playing less. Like he was like less interaction there. And you mentioned that the feeling that it gave you was when you go to a restaurant, for example, what are the very first time and you get this very nice meal? And when you go for the second one, like there's something's not like the same?

Observer 2 31:23

Yeah, it's like, you know, "I had a very nice experience, I want to have that nice experience again.... something is off"

Interviewer 31:30

something is off...

Observer 2 31:32

Something is off. You're nice, but not as nice as before.

Interviewer 31:36

And you said, okay, so he seems to understand; he understood this, that this there was something different,

Observer 2 31:44

I believe so. Yeah.

Interviewer 31:46

And you also mentioned before that he was when he was hitting very fast. So we're going back a little bit. He was getting fast, and he was getting what was happening?

Observer 2 31:58

Yeah, I really, I really think he was.

Interviewer 32:04

Could you guess tell me,

Observer 2 32:06

No, I, you know, the, the more you make me think about it, of course, I wonder out to what extent of course, it was understanding what's going on. So it's like, okay, the more I... as I can see something like this, okay, the faster I do, the higher the pitch. But the mayor thing is that I saw him doing that, again, trying to retrigger the same experience makes me feel that he was there understanding in his own way, what's going on. Sorry, to be a little bit messy...

Interviewer 32:49

Perfect. you go just go. And my work is then making sense of this. So you just go like, all the out you want, that's fine. You're focusing on that experience? And it's like,

Observer 2 33:01

yeah, so that's... again, that's that that's just my, my feeling about that. That moment, that is, of course, you know, you have the kid in front of you, you you don't know, to what extent they can understand what's going on. But not because they are not, I mean, it's just because, you know, I designed it. So I of course, a completely different [pause]... different understanding of it, because I made it... in terms of interaction, but the you know, these things like he's hitting faster, and then nice, and then he's doing that, again, makes me think that he is associating that he does something a certain way something else will happen. And that's enough. Yeah. It's, it's completely enough. It's what it's what all the thing was, was the Okay, once that back, it's, it's enough. So that's why I'm saying I think he was, you know, getting what was happening in try to repeat it. And that's why I say that when he was trying to repeat it, and then the kind of response from the installation was not the same because we turn up the vibration off... that's why it is saw I think I saw him doing less and less like, okay. Okay, it changed. It's not as cool as before, maybe I will not do it, or I will do it in a different way. So, yes.

Interviewer 34:49

So you're saying that she was like, okay, he was eating like this eating like to use the same metaphor. But then he wasn't like as enthusiastic. You also mentioned that ... correct me if I'm wrong, that it was like the same thing, but it was. I mean, it wasn't the same anymore. But it was enough. You said I think that's the point.

Observer 2 35:15

No, okay, sorry, the thing about enough, it was more on. I was doing this kind of super quick comparison between me approaching the string and a kid approaching the string. My approach the string is, is, of course, very, very different because I designed the kind of interaction. So to say, the faster you touch the string, the higher is the pitch. I did it. I know. So I know that, even if this string is not doing that, I know why. Because I coded it.

Interviewer 35:54

Yes.

Observer 2 35:55

The kid is completely unaware of this. He's just in front of the string is touching. And he needs to make sense of what's happening. Yes. So he's creating his own reality, and it's all understanding. And I don't know, what was his reality in that moment, his understanding? My feeling is that it was a in any case enough for me to say, I think he's enjoying and getting what's going on. This is what I was mean by it's, it's enough.

Interviewer 36:32

What do you think that in his interaction was enough? Specifically? Let's try to see.

Observer 2 36:39

So can you repeat this?

Interviewer 36:40

So what do you think that from his interaction with the string was telling you? That was enough?

Observer 2 36:51

I think you know. You know, I am starting thinking that probably enough is not the best word actually in is context. Because enough is also something like means that something is incomplete or partial. And something else a kind of negative connotation. That is not absolutely not what I'm saying here. So maybe I should try to find another word. But yeah, let's let's, let's for the moment use enough. But I'm not saying that is incomplete. I'm saying, I'm not saying that is negative, okay, just just make very sure. But you know, when you're talking with someone, and just talking about random things, and then you're not getting everything, but you get the other person's happy. And you say, it's enough for me... in that sense, you know, so it's a positive connotation. It's not like, it's enough, I understand that you're happy, I'm happy with you. It's enough for me, I don't need to understand more. That is kind of the connotation I want to have for the word enough. Now going deeper into this, also you want it was something you stopped me from just going around too much.

Interviewer 38:21

I will. No worries. Keep going...

Observer 2 38:26

to me the thing that he was there, and he was touching, the pitch was going up, and I saw his body moving a little bit faster around the string and then adding this kind of little high pitched scream at the end when you're happy about something. I thought, actually I don't... he's happy about what's going on. He he gets that he does A, B is happening more or less and is kind of trying to repeat it. Great [laughs]
So yeah

Interviewer 39:14

okay, so this Okay, so we have lots of things here. So this enough that you mentioned, it's not a negative incompleteness, but it's more like a sensation of like, it's happy. So there was something in you that told? Okay.

Observer 2 39:31

Yeah, absolutely. It's absolutely not like it's not a sense of exactly ...as you say. It's not a sense of saying yes, something is partial here. It's incomplete. And something that is incomplete is by default bad... that I don't believe in general. But this is not the meaning is it was more like

Interviewer 39:54

it was enough in you for you.

Observer 2 39:56

Yeah, for me to say I think he's enjoined I think he's there, as I said before

Interviewer 40:10

so he's enjoying himself. Yeah. So he is like hitting fast. And he was like smiling. What happened then?

Observer 2 40:21

In me, or what did you see?

Interviewer 40:24

What did you see?

Observer 2 40:26

Where he was?

Interviewer 40:27

Yeah, play. So he was playing and he was happy. And he, like made this "haha" just right after that, after the last from for example.

Observer 2 40:38

Yeah, for example I think that [pause] I think he just tried to repeat it. Like, he reached this kind of pitched moment. And he was hitting faster and faster, probably trying to reach even higher pitches or just to add more vibration, because of course, each time they hit the string, the platform vibrates. quite strong. So... So.... So So yes, I think that no, I think I think, you know, if he was repeating that he was like, this kind of... [pause] climax moment in which you're helping, then you express your happiness in this little scream and a bit of clapping or whatever. And then I think it was trying to just repeat it, and do the same. And here, since I coded, I know that when he was trying to do that, and he was trying to repeat the theme, you know too faster, this was not enough for the string to go back to the beginning of the interaction. I mean, it starts from a low pitch, and then raises up to high pitch, the faster you do, and then it has this kind of decay moment. So if you leave the string for a couple of seconds, it slowly go back to the basic pitch. I think that while this was going back, he was interacting again. So it was not enough time. Okay, this enough. Now, it's different enough, because not enough time for the

installation, to go to the basic moment. And then to recreate the exact same rise of pitch, because he was already doing that he was doing fast and fast, because he was enjoying that. So this is what I noticed, like, oh, well, maybe he wants to create these kinds of escalation again. And it just needs a little bit more of seconds in the installation. But I believe that he wanted to repeat it. So that's why he was there. clapping, smiling, screaming and then repeating it. Yeah. I mean, eventually, it worked also, because it goes down and then restart, but I noticed that... [pause] you know, the [pause] the time in between these two, repetition was very, very close, like, just wanted to do that again. I mean, we can just say that very easily, you know, I really believe that he wanted to do that again, and and they noticed that the pitch was staying high, because because how the solution was coded. So that's all

Interviewer 44:05

I mean, they he... got in any case, the vibration, so it didn't change anything in terms of vibration, he really, he still got it, because every time you touch it, it vibrates. But I think he was enjoying maybe also this kind of pitch going up. So you're saying that the pitch, okay, so you have your perspective as a designer of this piece. So when you go and hit this faster, so the pitch goes higher, but then if you stopped like, hitting it goes down. There is a small like middle time there. And you're saying that he was like, sort of he was going fast. And correct me if I'm wrong, but there were some moments where he where he stopped sometimes for little like moments that weren't enough to sort of decrease like In 100%,

Observer 2 45:00

yeah, the pitch

Interviewer 45:01

So he was like creating a sort of escalations, right. And then clapping and smiling. So it was like this idea that you were saying in the beginning of "getting it", it might be also related to this, like sort of playing with the pitch.

Observer 2 45:19

Yeah, that's that's the thing. Yeah. Because when he was reaching this high pitch, I mean, he was keep keep hitting faster. So I even thought in this moment, like, I don't know, maybe it would have been even nicer to just go forever up but with the pitches, maybe just enjoying that so much [pause]. I mean, maybe I'm just thinking this now I don't know. But you know, now that I'm thinking about it, he was in enjoying that, I believe that those are the pitch was racing. So when at certain point, the pitch stops... the pitch, the pitch stops raising, you know, just in terms of design choice. And who knows, I don't know. Maybe he wanted the beach to go higher, higher higher forever. I don't know.

Interviewer 46:25

okay, so now I'll do a little recap of the whole I will try I will try because this always difficult that you were identifying three specific moments. So the first one was with this girl that it was in the corner, and I was sad that you were a little bit worried, but then you received the confirmation that she was okay. Second kid, there was in the second platform, I think, who was like very happy and he was like, there was the first kid you saw but then finally, we decided focusing on the third kid he was in the bigger platform, I think a big chunk of the conversation was like on his experience that you noticed that he was

playing with the string and he went faster and faster. And as he was creating like this sort of escalations with the timing, but you are also under the impression that he was like hitting faster and faster so... sort of triggers this idea of what if I create like an installation like a sound experience that goes this goes up and up? So he was like, hitting faster there was like this little moments and he was like clapping and laughing. But then there was another moment where he just turned off the vibration the haptics and he was like you notice certain like kind of disappointment as if for example, you go to a restaurant or in first time and you have like a nice meal and then the second one is like there's something off here; he was like you noticed that he was hitting with less intensity like there was something... not not like the same kind of energy is there anything like this like really really broad because you have like so many descriptions here! But is there anything else you might want to add or something that you want to sort of correct, rectify something that I didn't get right?

Observer 2 48:31

On this or even more in general

Interviewer 48:35

on this, in general. [pause] but that's okay. Because if... you wanna say something?

Observer 2 48:57

no, I was I was just you know, thinking again about these use of the word enough.

Interviewer 49:03

I was like, going back to you?

Observer 2 49:06

Yes. I have an interpretation of what was happening we are enough but it's not my role to interpret your enough... maybe after the interview. But my enough is you know, I used to different enough. I said that because one enough is you know, "this bottle is not full enough". I mean, it's there. It's enough... is not. The other enough is not there. It's not like "okay, I have this kind of measurement". And then I'm saying that is not fulfilling some kind of any is... absolutely not that. Is a... is, as I tried to say before, it's not to say that something was not complete is it's to say, I don't know what's going on really, because I cannot be in the kid's mind. I just think that for me is enough to say, I'm happy. And I believe that kids are in good time. So

Interviewer 50:25

where do you feel that "enough"? So when you try to for example, if you're in front of the kids, they are happy. And you are okay. That's there is a confirmation that that's enough. How do you feel that "enough"?

Observer 2 50:45

I don't know. Maybe someone is.

Interviewer 50:47

Perhaps it feels somewhere in the body?

Observer 2 50:50

yeah yeah. It's like... I feel... okay. This is because I am worried. And then something happened and then they feel relieved as a it's enough. It's an cool with thar. It's enough like [pause] it's, like, do we have time?

Interviewer 51:21

Yes, we have time.

Observer 2 51:23

Just just want to find the right comparison. Because let's do it. It's like... you know, it's, it's broad, it's much more saying something about me rather than the others this feeling of enough like, okay, so so you're good. Okay, fine. So, yeah, this feeling of you feel a little bit of relief, like, okay, because I was worried that you were not enjoying you were not having good time, or that this was uncomfortable, but okay. Or maybe that the interaction is too complicated, just messy is confusing. It's impossible to get what's going on? Unless you've coded. "Ah no, oh, ah no, you.... okay [breath out in relief]. It's enough. I've had enough in that kind of sentence. Again, it's probably saying much more important than others.

Interviewer 52:26

That's perfect. This is what we are looking for. Okay, your perception as because, I mean, just closing the interview. But... through this interview, the idea is to get what you were feeling and perceiving. And you have different roles. So I didn't ask you to like, "describe as a designer or a composer", I didn't ask you to describe... your description was as an observer, but at the same time as you're the composer, you're still embedded is absolutely your description anyways. So it happens also with [Observer 3], for example, she is like she looks after the kids. And her descriptions as an observer are like embedded and that sort of influenced by the fact that she's like, of course, with [Observer1]. The same thing. She has like a different role. And still, yeah, so I don't need to tell you. Oh, you know, it's like, you put like the composer's hat. What's gonna happen; it's gonna appear. But thanks a lot. I shouldn't be evaluating the individual. This is very rich.

Observer 2 53:31

I hope it was good enough.

Interviewer 53:36

Yeah, believe me, this is great. This is great, great, great. Sometimes it's kind of I will stop here this something that happens with this....